

DESIGN KNOWLEDGE AS INTERACTION BETWEEN FORM AND SHAPE. A PEDAGOGIC CASE STUDY.

*“...yet art plainly calls for both feeling and reasoning.”**

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Abstract. Designing with a computer means to establish meaningful relationships between form and shape. It is necessary to develop computer tools that narrow the gap that still persists between the perceived form and the computer representation of a shape. We present a set of prototype tools to create two-dimensional compositions, whose purpose is to facilitate the interaction between designer and computer. The tools have been used to teach architecture students some fundamental implications in the use of computers to design.

1. Introduction

In the literature about computers and design, the terms ‘form’ and ‘shape’ are often used indistinctively. A geometric construct, created with the aid of a CAD program, might be referred as a complex ‘form’. Such ‘form’ is considered to be the product of the computer; or, at least, something that it could not have been created without it. Design (e.g. the culturally meaningful creation of form in the artist’s mind)¹ is then assimilated to a geometric construction generated by, or with the help of, the procedures established in a computer program. Shape supplants form, whereas the computer supported procedures confront the creative power of the artist’s mind. Ultimately, behind the failure to distinguish between form and shape, lies the indeterminate relationship between designer and computer in the design process.

In order to clarify the role of computers in design practice and education it would help to establish a distinction between the terms form and shape. As a frame of reference in this discussion we have taken up the following ontological commitment: form is only perceived by the mind, while the structure of a shape can be captured by a computer². When an artist creates with a computer, an interaction between the form as perceived (e.g. imagined, understood) in the mind and the shape as represented on the computer is taking place. In this context, design knowledge is the result of a dialectic relationship between subjective and objective dimensions of form³. Designing with a computer means, therefore, to integrate both cognitive dimensions -objective, subjective- in the design process.⁴

* Max Bill, *The Mathematical Way of Thinking in the Visual Art of our Time*, 1949. Reprinted in Emmer (1995).

Ideally, a fluid dialogue between designer and computer would facilitate the systematic exploration of variations within a particular formal structure, as well as the discovery of new ones. But neither the computer tools nor the artist's mental processes seem to facilitate that dialogue. To achieve a more effective relationship between the designer and computer (e.g. between form and shape) it is necessary: 1. to develop more intuitive tools that close the gap that actually exists between mental and computer representations 2. to educate designers to integrate those tools into their thinking process. These are the two goals we have set up for this pedagogic case study.

The work we are presenting is an investigation on visual thinking, aimed at developing and applying innovative computer tools and methods to the education of design. This research work, therefore, is biased by our pedagogic goals: we have delimited the scope of our investigations so that the issues we address and the results we produce are pedagogically meaningful.

2. Systems of Representation: FIGURE

The course *Sistemas de Representación* (Systems of Representation), is taught during the second and third-year class of our Architecture School. Representation is the subject matter of this course. Around the concept of representation, we have created a conceptual framework that embraces a variety of disciplines: *gestaltung*, graphic design, communication, aesthetics, philosophy and computing. The course is divided into six themes, each one dedicated to a representation system: TEXT, FIGURE, IMAGE, OBJECT, SPACE and LIGHT. The exercises of the course are done individually and collaboratively, using the web-based learning environment SDR: NETWORKING, specifically designed for this course.

In the theme FIGURE, we address a series of fundamental issues regarding the perception and creation of abstract compositions of two-dimensional colored shapes, among them: vocabulary and rules of composition, transformations (symmetry, fractals), figure and ground, shape and color, abstraction and figuration, icons and symbols. We illustrate some of these concepts with explanations of the works from artists like Van Doesburg, Mondrian, Itten, Albers, Klee, Lohse and Bill. And we expect students to explore further the issues addressed in the lectures through a series of exercises on two-dimensional composition with the computer.

The tools the students use to make the exercises are standard vector and raster graphic programs, as well a computer application we have developed especially for the exercises of this theme: I-GRID (intuitive grid), that will be described later in this article. This way, using a variety of computer programs, students can understand the possibilities and limitations that each tool has in the form generation process.

3. Exercises.

The exercises, carried out over a two-month period, are structured in a three-step sequence: 1. Interpretation of an abstract composition 2. Creation of a composition using standard tools 3. Creation of a composition using I-GRID.

1. INTERPRETATION: individual exercise, using standard vector and raster standard graphic programs (2 weeks)

The first part of the exercise consisted of the analysis of a composition by Richard Paul Lohse (Figure 1). Lohse's work illustrates the creative power of the structure inherent to a composition. A beholder, confronted to one of these modular compositions, becomes engaged in a creative process by which an endless number of formal configurations emerge in the act of perception.⁵

Figure 1. Paintings by Richard Paul Lohse.

We asked students to analyze the structure of Lohse's works, describing their compositional rules (Figure 2) and the perceptual effect on the beholder (Figure 3) with an animation⁶. With this exercise, we wanted to educate the eye of the student before starting the exercise in composition.⁷

Figure 2. Recreation of a composition by Lohse after its rules of composition. Snapshots of an animation. Student: Alicia Pellicer, SDR 00/01.

Figure 3. Interpretation of the perceptual effect on the eye of the beholder. Snapshots of an animation. Student: Pep Rubí, SDR 00/01.

2. COMPOSITION: individual and collaborative exercise, using standard graphic programs (4 weeks)

After the analysis and interpretation, students created their own abstract compositions. The compositions were developed as a series of variations on a theme of their choice (e.g. depth, rhythm, symmetry, twist...)⁸ (Figure 4) With this exercise, they should cultivate their capacity for visual reasoning, finding equilibrium between inventiveness and systematic thinking.⁹

4. Visual, non-visual structures

The image displayed by the computer is the visual manifestation of a non-visual representation, built up with the procedures provided by the program. There are, therefore, two distinct structures in a shape created on the computer: one visual, equivalent to any other visual image we perceive in the world; the other propositional, codified in a language suitable to computation.

What is then difference between perceiving a composition that has been painted on a canvas and one constructed with a computer program? Let's take one of the works from Lohse (e.g. an actual painting). The multiplicity of structures (Gestalts) that are potentially contained in the painting, unfold in the mind of the beholder as a result of the act of perception.¹⁰ These structures, however, do not exist by themselves: they are materialized in the painting and embedded in the visual image. The situation is different if we consider the perception of a comparable composition created with a computer tool. In this case, there is a visual image as well as a non-visual representation of it (e.g. explicit description of elements that make the composition, relations between them, groups of elements). Thus, as we perceive the image displayed on the computer, it might occur that the dominant Gestalt matches the internal structuring of the shape, or not. Such a possibility would not come about in the perception of the actual painting.¹¹

When, instead of the pure act of perception, we consider the design process, the correspondence between the structure as perceived in the mind and the structure as represented in the computer becomes a crucial issue. Because, in the course of that process, the designer is continuously modifying the object of design to conform it to the dominant Gestalt at a given stage. With manual techniques, alternatives might be quickly explored with sketches, for example. With standard graphic programs, on the other hand, the implicit structure of the shape might impose some restrictions to the changes it can undergo. If the prevalent Gestalt is consistent with the existing structure, then the designer can explore alternative configurations, perhaps in a more exhaustive and faster way than it could be done with manual techniques. However, if the Gestalt that the designer has in mind no longer corresponds with the inner structuring of the shape, the computer is likely to become a hindrance rather than an aid.¹²

At this point, we might be confronting a dilemma: 1. to have highly structured shapes on the computer, which would allow the quick generation of variations, even automatically, as in generative modeling. In this case, the pay-off is, in our view, that form is reduced to shape whereas some essential quality of art might get lost in the way¹³ 2. to have lowly structured shapes, whose internal relationships can be determined by the user in function of the prevalent Gestalt, as it occurs with a general-purpose program. In this case, there is a risk to use the computer as a pure drafting tool, taking little advantage of its capacity to represent shape differently than with manual techniques.

A compromise solution to get away from this dilemma would be the one we have adopted with the tool I-GRID: to have special purpose tools, that support creation and edition of a particular class of shapes, by means of simple and intuitive operators that allow the designer to explore a particular design space in close interaction with the tool.

5. I-GRID, intuitive grid

To understand the scope of the tool I-GRID, let's consider the step-by-step construction of a shape (a square symmetrically divided into four parts, as depicted in the figures surrounded by dotted

lines) using a computer tool (Figure 6). The same shape is created in three different ways: A, starting with a square and applying a transformation that divides it into four equal parts; B, dividing the same figure vertically into two equal columns which are in turn divided into two equal rows; C, starting with a smaller shape, which is then copied and rotated.

As we observe the square divided into four equal parts on the computer display, without being aware of the underlying construction process, we can perceive a variety of possible configurations, according to the laws of perceptual organization. Eventually, some of them could correspond to one of the three processes considered. As we proceed to act upon the shape to transform it, its unique internal representation becomes manifest. Once we are aware of the structure of the shape, we can continue modifying it. Following with procedure A, we could now select one of the four squares and subdivide it into four parts, and then repeat the same operation with one of the resulting cells. According to B, we could subdivide a column (consisting of two squares) into four equal columns and a row into three equal rows. And as for C, we could keep copying individual cells.

Figure 6. Three processes to construct the same shape and the subsequent transformations of it.

I-GRID is an application that supports the creation of shapes according to each one the three processes described above. It is composed of three tools, each one based on a distinct data structure: I-GRID [T], has a tree-structure; I-GRID [M], a matrix structure; and I-GRID [U], is un-structured.

5.1. I-GRID [T]

I-GRID [T] is based on the principle of nested shapes: a cell can be recursively divided into four cells. The composition process is internally represented as a tree structure. We begin drawing a rectangular shape, which then can be divided into four equal parts by simply clicking on it (Figure 7). Each one of the new cells can be divided in turn into four cells, and this process can be repeated indefinitely with only the click of a mouse button (Figure 8). The color of the starting shape, is also ‘divided’ into the four new cells, giving rise to a color degradation following a default color scale. Alternatively, one can choose a different color scale to be applied to each new group of four cells.

Figure 7. The first four steps of a composition process using I-GRID [T].

The editing operations are: dividing, mirroring, and rotating a cell; erasing a division (i.e. removing a children from its parent in the tree-like data structure) and editing the overall figure's width and height parameters. These transformations can be performed at any level of nesting (Figure 9). Simply pressing the space, the user can move up and down the tree structure of the shape and select the level where the editing transformation will be applied. The program's user interface is fairly simple: all the operators fit in one dialog box (Figure 10).

Figure 8. Diagram showing the nesting of shapes constructed with I-GRID [T]

Figure 9. Rotation and symmetry applied to the second nesting level of the composition shown in Figure 8.

Figure 10. The dialogue box of I-GRID [T]

5.2 I-GRID [M]

Whereas the data structure of I-GRID [T] is a tree, I-GRID [M] is a matrix. The data structure of I-GRID [T] contains individual cells but does not recognize higher-order elements like ‘row’ or ‘column’. In I-GRID [M], on the other hand, an isolated cell does not exist: it is always part of a column and a row.

With this tool, a rectangular shape is divided into any number of rows and columns of variable height and width. We can think of the initial shape as a grid consisting of one column and one row, which are then subdivided into more columns and rows (Figure 11). This operation of subdivision can be applied recursively too. Grid lines can be translated -by simple pick and drag- and removed (XXXX). Grid lines and fill colors can be toggled on and off. All editing operators are placed in one dialog box (Figure 12).

Figure 11. The division of a column into 4 columns, in I-GRID [M].

6. The limits of formal exploration

The creative process can be thought of as a dialectic between two apparently opposite goals: to establish some limits to the formal exploration, and to overcome them by exhausting all formal possibilities that those limits encompass.¹⁴ With I-GRID, the embedded structure, and the associated procedures to transform it, set the limits to formal exploration. In this context, the designer can put all the creative efforts in exploring the universe of formal variations with the procedures provided by the tool¹⁵. Thus, rather than limiting creativity, I-GRID might even facilitate it.¹⁶ Besides, the loose structuring of the shapes leaves to the designer enough space for exploration.¹⁷

Right from the start, a designer using an I-GRID tool is working with shapes endowed with certain structure. Because of this, it is not necessary go through a phase of imagining a design (e.g. making it visible to oneself) and then representing it (e.g. making it visible to others), as it is typically the case with manual techniques. Rather, the act of imagination can be postponed for a later stage in the design process, as shapes begin to emerge through the interaction with the tool.

The limits that creativity demands are not only determined by the computer tools. The influence of precedents and the conscious or unconscious adherence of the artist to them, also impose some limits to creativity, either in a positive sense (providing a space for continuing formal invention) or in a negative sense (preventing the appearance of alternative formal spaces). Those precedents might condition the aesthetic will of the creator in a more powerful manner than any computer tool does.

7. Student work

In the COMPOSITION assignment, we realized that students were using the standard graphic programs mostly as drafting tools. They did not even give much meaning to the control of the inner structure of the shapes they created. Rather, they made compositions in the most intuitive manners: reproducing on the computer what they had previously imagined and represented with other techniques. But, the most critical issue of designing with a computer -achieving an identity between the structure of the shape on the computer and the form in the mind during the design process- was being neglected.

We thought, that with a tool like I-GRID we could better fulfill this pedagogic goal: to make a student aware of the fact that designing with a computer requires working with formal structures that are meaningful both for the computer and for the designer. Then, an interweaving of computer structures and mental structures could start to transform the design thinking and hence, the design work.

We prepared a two-hour exercise with I-GRID for a group of forty-six third students in the third year class. The goal of the exercise was to achieve a connection between design thinking and inner structure of the shapes, as recognized by the program. We asked students to create a series of compositions on a given theme (center, rhythm, symmetry, infinite...) using the I-GRID tool of their choice. The modes of operation of the three applications and the differences between them were explained in a previous class. Ten students chose I-GRID [T], thirty-five [M], and only one chose [U].

On a first inspection of the results, we observed that most of them looked visually satisfying to us: they conveyed a coherent formal exploration of a theme, with controlled proportions, purposeful use of color as composition element, and, above all, many of the works had some personal touch, which contrasted with the systematic built-in procedures (Figures 16-18). Obviously, the question to ask is how much should be credited to the student's visual skills and how much to the program. We believe that both factors contributed to some degree. The two previous assignments (INTERPRETATION, COMPOSITION) trained the eye of the students to work within a particular formal universe of compositions. Then, providing some powerful and intuitive tools to explore that universe, did the rest.

Other issues we were interested to assess had to do with the congruency between the works produced and the tool employed. We could expect, that all compositions created with a particular tool would share some formal properties. In other words, we thought that we could easily identify which one of the three programs had been used to create a composition. But, this was not always the case.

It is true that almost every exercise done with I-GRID [T] (Figure16) reflects the formal logic built in that tool. In particular, the 'fractal look' that stems from the recursive built-in procedures, the heterogeneous grain that results from the subdivision operation, and the dispersed focal points, are present in most compositions. But there are also other works that, apparently, could have been created with other I-GRID tool. For example, the works in Figure 16a,c could have been done with I-GRID [M].

Figure 16. Exercises done with I-GRID [T]. Students: (a) Lluisa Silla (b) Josep Torrent (c) Alicia Pellicer (d) Marcos López

The works produced with I-GRID [M], are characterized by their linearity; a quality that stems from the data structure built in this tool that recognizes not only cells, but also rows and columns. (Figure 17). We can observe that some students used I-GRID [M] in a rather conventional way, filling cells with color, as if they would be working with a raster graphics program (Figure 17c). Others, however, took better advantage of the capacities of the application to operate on a grid structure (Figure 17a,d). And, as it occurred with the exercises done with I-GRID [T], there were also works that, at a first sight, looked as if they would have been created with another I-GRID tool. For example, the compositions in Figure 17b have the formal qualities characteristic of I-GRID [T] (focal concentration resulting from recursivity)

Figure 17. Exercises done with I-GRID [M]. Students: (a) Carlos Fragoso (b) Jordi Azpeleta (c) Gerard Ribot (e) Apolonia Salvà

Finally, the only work done using I-GRID [U] looks very much as an outcome of I-GRID [M]. The broken contour that would distinguish the shapes created with this tool is missing in this compact grid. (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Exercise done with I-GRID [U]. Student: Toni Cañas

Needless to say, further work is necessary to understand, and take advantage of, the creative potential of the tools we have created. Both, students and teachers, need to become more experienced with them. In this regard, the works that we have presented should be considered the result of a first contact with the tools.

7. Conclusions

We have presented a comprehensive case study of pedagogic research aimed at integrating computation and design education, which embraces: 1. theoretical content 2. individual and collaborative exercises, and 3. special purpose tools that support a particular form of design thinking. We have made the case that, to be pedagogically significant, a computer tool must be imbued in certain theoretical framework.

Ultimately, the purpose of using computers in design education is to educate the eye of the beholder, that is to say, to develop his or her capacity for visual understanding. With computers, this can be done in more sophisticated ways than with other techniques. However, our vision is culturally influenced in such a way that, even if a possibility exists for a computer tool to give rise to something 'radically new', this will not exist unless the beholder is able to recognize certain aesthetic and epistemological significance on the perceived shapes.

The aesthetic of the digital age, therefore, will be the result of a subtle interweaving between the artist's talent to understand form and the computer's capacity to represent shape. As far it concerns to artistic creation, the mere application of a computer tool will not bring about any substantial changes, neither in design thinking nor in the forms that result from them. Art -with or without computers- it is always about form, not shape.

¹⁴ As Boden has claimed, “The artist or scientist may explore a certain style of thinking so as to uncover its potential and identify its limits” (Boden 1992, p. 47). This exploration continues until “...the rules have been well and truly tested, so that the generative potential of the style is reasonably clear, boredom and/or curiosity invite a change in the rules” (Boden 1992, p. 48).

¹⁵ In this regard, the I-GRID tool could represent to the model of ‘matrix’ and ‘code’ proposed by Koestler (1989) to explain creativity. For Koestler, a ‘matrix’ is a pattern of ordered behavior, flexible and adaptable to the environmental conditions, which is governed by a ‘code’ of rules. The matrix is flexible, but the rules are fixed. In our program, the matrix would correspond to the formal universe supported by each tool, while the code would be the built-in rules of transformation.

¹⁶ The fact that a computer can produce any number of variations does not necessarily makes it more creative than the artist. As Reichardt already noticed, “With computer art, at least that which is produced by writing a program, the artist must know exactly what it is he wants to do and in what areas he is permitting randomness to occur. All this has to be done before the actual image emerges. With action painting, the program is being written as the work on the picture proceeds. This is true to a lesser or greater extent of most pictures, although it is the element of chance in action painting that is always stressed, as indeed it is also the one which is emphatically pointed out by those who produced drawings with the aid of computers.” (Reichardt 1971, pp. 88-89).

¹⁷ According to Hofstadter, it would not be necessary to exhaust all formal possibilities of a particular conceptual space for someone to become disinterested in it, as Boden claims. Rather, he thinks that “you get bored with something not when you have exhausted its repertoire of behavior, but when you have mapped out the limits of the space that contains its behavior” (Hofstadter 1979, p. 621). Because of their loose structure, it is unlikely that a designer using I-GRID tools would quickly map their limits.

Acknowledgements

I-GRIDS [T] and [U] have been programmed by Álvaro Sicilia. I-GRID [M] was programmed by Joan M. Quílez. The three programs run under AutoCAD 2000, and have been written in C++, using the Object ARX libraries from Autodesk.

References

- Arnheim, R. (1974) *Art and Visual Perception*. University of California Press, Berkeley [etc.]
- Bill, M. (1995) The Mathematical Way of Thinking in the Visual Art of our Time. In Emmer, M. (ed.) *The Visual Mind: Art and Mathematics*. The MIT Press, Cambridge [etc.]
- Boden, M. (1992) *The Creative Mind*. Abacus, London.
- Chase, S. (1997) Emergency, Creativity and Computational Tractability in Shape Grammars. In *Proceedings of Interactive Systems for Supporting the Emergence of Concepts and Ideas, CHI'97*, Atlanta, March 1997.
- Edmonds, E., Moran, T. and Do, E. (1998) Interactive Systems for Supporting the Emergence of Concepts and Ideas. *SIGCHI Bulletin*30(1).
- Hofstadter, D. R. (1979) *Gödel, Escher, Bach: an Eternal Golden Braid*. Basic Books, London.
- Kepes, G. (1947) *Language of Vision*. Paul Theobald, Chicago.